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Lenin and the Law
(A case-study on the borders of legal normality)

Marxist revolutionaries used to dedicate whole lifetimes to fight *the* enemy, the prevailing political and economic structure, believing breakthrough to be victory, and device to stand for purpose. Considering their position exhausted in agitation, the actual task of building a new society could not be on their practical agenda yet. Captive of the dogmatism of “Religion and law are the ideologies of the suppressing classes, the latter gradually replacing the former”, they were interested solely in a state and law withering away. Therefore not even law-graduate Lenin concerned with law in general and its strategic potential for state building in particular. Won into power, he made law used for tactical reasons in daily changes exclusively, in cases it was considered able to benefit the revolutionary cause. As an empty form for mass mobilisation or simple complementation to terror, it turned to become nothing but the direct means, or extension, of politics. In territories once bolshevised, it has never transformed into an autonomous phenomenon of social mediation, well-received by society at large as one of the main civilising factors. No wonder if it resulted in tsarist ukaz-government changed into Leninist decree-government, led by the Bolshevik party as a private organisation. In comparison, the victims’ death toll due to Bolshevism meant sixteen times as many victims’ lives as the last half of a century of tsarism. In sum, it was only good to fruit “legalised lawlessness” in the past and the lookalike of a dual state in the present.

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1. Introduction: The Chances of Evaluation

One of the prerequisites of investigations on the field of social sciences is whether or not what we name as subject of investigation does indeed have a perceivably identifiable reference in reality. This is a preliminary issue for any generalization and conceptualization. At the same time, anything that emerges in real life is unique and ultimately unrepeatable, since everything that exists or prevails is, in point of principle, a configuration assembled from infinite components and networks of relationships. Moreover, what we name in and by it is not exactly just its self but the analogon of something that—as reminiscent of—has already been named. And from this reality as an infinite hotchpotch of complexities made up of components and relationships, exclusively that part or aspect will be distinguished and named as distinct from anything else which are

worth distinguishing and naming, according to some associated human interest.¹ Consequently, if all that emerges in life embodies such a theoretically indefinite complexity and inexhaustibility, then the intent of modern anthropology (forerun by DESCARTES as to the ideals of science and by LEIBNIZ with his conceptual formulation of universality²) to build a comprehensive inventory of the constituents of social formations cannot be else than an airy dream, as it would assume that anything that has ever been must have been just one piece out of such inventory.³

From the field of law, let's take the example of social products of the second nature or those qualities that social conventionalization may generate (in language, customs and institutions, among others): obviously, neither naming nor alleged qualities can cover more than the very act of ascribing some properties to them. In general, it is their conventionalized understanding and interpretation that can in any contexture serve as their sole foundation and explanation. Let's ask: are we analyzing phenomenal forms of law? Are we talking about ways of how to practice law? Only one answer can be taken as granted: their case is certainly not a simple description. For there is no neutral position available that would stand above everything, from which we, external observers, could objectively overview and judge. From the first moment we have already been participants. And only doing so can we build ideas and explanations through making logically erected distinctions, considered from functional or structural points of view or approached by systemic schemes projected onto the subject.

For instance, when I was to carry out theoretical researches on codification developed from the law's universal history, I had to answer prealably how I could draw the different ways and proceedings of different ages and legal regimes within a common notional set, when I cannot have other criterion than the role I find they have played, that is, a function by which I qualify them exteriorly and posteriorly?⁴ A few decades later, I was to formulate some dichotomization in legal development in order to characterize the zigzags and

¹ As reflected upon the notion of the 'fact', see Csaba Varga *The Paradigms of Legal Thinking* [1996/1999] enlarged 2nd ed. (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 418 [Philosophiae Iuris] & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14600/14657/>>.

² Cf. Csaba Varga 'Leibniz und die Frage der rechtlichen Systembildung' in *Materialismus und Idealismus im Rechtsdenken* Geschichte und Gegenwart, hrsg. Karl A. Mollnau (Stuttgart: Franz Steiner Verlag Wiesbaden 1987), 114–127 [Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie, Beiheft 31] {reprint in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15300/15333/#>>, 219–232}.

³ Cf. Claude Lévi-Strauss *Leçon inaugurale faite le mardi 5 janvier 1960* ([Paris]: Collège de France 1960) 47; overviewed by Alan Jenkins *The Social Theory of Claude Lévi-Strauss* (London: Macmillan 1979) 193, part 1, and Tzvetan Todorov 'Levi-Strauss' in *New French Thought* Political Philosophy, ed. Mark Lilla (Princeton: Princeton University Press 1994), 37–53.

⁴ Csaba Varga *Codification as a Socio-historical Phenomenon* [1979/1991] 2nd ed. with an Annex & Postscript (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2011) viii + 431 & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14200/14231/>>; further developed by his 'Ősnépeink jogszemlélete' [The concept of law of our ancestor peoples] *Hitel* XXVIII (2015) 11, 83–96 & <<http://www.hitelfolyoirat.hu/sites/default/files/pdf/17-varga.pdf>> and his 'Taxonomy of Law and Legal Mapping: Patterns and Limits of the Classification of Legal Systems' *Acta Juridica Hungarica* 51 (2010) 4 & in <http://real-j.mtak.hu/765/1/ACTAJURIDICA_51.pdf>, 253–272.

swings between the law's rigid enforcement and the intent at making it more livable.⁵ As a matter of fact, especially now when particular legal orders happen to be thoroughly criticized for political or ideological reason alone, the merits of criticism are often exemplified by one side of the above complementarity, as if it were an excess itself, although the two sides' concurrence—either simultaneous prevalence or unceasing fight for domination—is inherent in the legal arrangements of practically all ages and cultures; and this is independent of the fact whether or not the legal technique concerned may be regarded as a step toward nihilization or, just to the contrary, over-politicization of the law.⁶

What can be the main lesson one may draw from all this? Well, it seems that all we can feel ourselves at home in the milieu and surroundings we live, and consequently, knowing others' "home" is like Munchausen's act of saving himself from drowning by pulling on his own hair, that is, bridging the gap so that "I interpret your culture through my culture". After all, anyone can only penetrate anyone/anything other with his/her own self. And such a knowing can only be a process incapable of self-justification: justification can exclusively be hoped from a series of feedback gained over time.⁷ For it is to realize that "A supranational legal science does not exist, an overworld does not exist, nor does a superior point of view to observe law."⁸

Accordingly, there is no universal point of view from which the criterion of social phenomena like law could exhaustively be explained with normative force. It follows, too, that nothing that could stand to the mean—i.e. normality or typicality—does exist in fact.⁹ If everything is related to one another and any statement concerning them is a function of a value judgment to be made, then we can rely on nothing but the accumulation of experience for that we may assess the relative (i.e. *hic et nunc*) worthiness of any occurrence for human practice.

Three decades ago I had the honor to deliver one of the plenary speeches at the World Congress of legal philosophers in Edinburgh. Now we know that it was close to the end of the Soviet rule; anyhow, I was expected also to talk on

⁵ Csaba Varga 'Buts et moyens en droit' in *Giovanni Paolo II Le vie della giustizia: Itinerari per il terzo millennio* (Omaggio dei giuristi a Sua Santità nel XXV anno di pontificato) a cura di Aldo Loiodice & Massimo Vari (Roma: Bardi Editore & Libreria Editrice Vaticana 2003), 71–75 {reprint in <<http://www.thomasinternational.org/hu/projects/step/conferences/20050712budapest/varga1.htm>>}.

⁶ Cf., e.g., Csaba Varga 'Múltkutatás, jövőkeresés Közép-Európa jogában' [Inquiry into the past, search for a future in the law of Central Europe] *Valóság* LVIII (2015) 7, 1–18 & <http://epa.oszk.hu/02900/02924/00031/pdf/EPA02924_valosag_2015_7_001-018.pdf>.

⁷ Csaba Varga '»Comparative Law and Multicultural Legal Classes: Challenge or Opportunity?«' [The General Reporter's Questionnaire to the General Topic 1 of the XXth World Congress of the International Academy of Comparative Law at Fukuoka in 2018] (January 17, 2017) 1–4 in <<http://gc.iuscomparatum.info/gc/project/comparative-law-and-multicultural-legal-classes-challenge-or-opportunity-english/>>; for the general report in Hungarian *in extenso*, Varga Csaba *Jogfilozófia a múlt, jelen és jövő ölelésében* (Budapest: Pázmány-Press 2018), 457–500 [Tanulmányok 44] & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/18900/18995/18995.pdf>>.

⁸ Pasquale Femia 'Criticism: From the Outskirts of a World without a Centre' *The Italian Law Journal* 1 (2017) 1 & <www.theitalianlawjournal.it>, 3–16 at 14–15.

⁹ Cf. Varga *The Paradigms*.

the nature of Socialist law. As to my intuition on the topic, I was certain about; but, yet, which standard do I have also to judge it? After all, I resorted to a rational construct by venturing an *ontological reconstruction*. Providing that we accept the reasonableness of considering law to be a relatively autonomous category as distinguished from anything else, where are its boundaries? According to a justifiable and simplest answer, law has emerged to be betwixt and between pressuring forces intending to hegemonize it. That is, law, from the mean, is to mediate.¹⁰ No party may master or absorb it. By this token, Socialist law is “far from being full-fledged; it is defective, faulty, and inferior”.¹¹

May we say, too, that a whole legal regime is deformed or degenerated? Obviously, any such statement would precondition some measuring by common standard, e.g. some ideality expressed as normality or typicality. Considering that legal regimes based on most varying ideals of *ordo* cannot be derived from one common denominator,¹² the only benchmark available is a practice deemed acceptable/desirable for our own use. No need to say that this is just the crossing point where social facts and their evaluation are to meet.¹³ Our assessment of either generative or degenerative will be a function of it.¹⁴

The present paper as a case study is not on some randomly selected historical personality. Instead, it is an attempt to reconstruct the formation of an extreme pole in the use of law, with effects leaving their imprint on huge a part of the world as well. Was there any exceptional necessity to dictate this? Or was it all just the unfortunate overlapping of forced steps? Our final conclusion will show that with functions and dysfunctions piling up, the path that was actually covered has proved to be dead end of the law’s civilizing mission, standing for the self-destruction of millennial dreams.

2. Preludes

¹⁰ The notion of mediation [*Vermittlung*] is a key concept in George Lukács’ posthumous *Towards the Ontology of Social Being*; cf. Csaba Varga *The Place of Law in George Lukács’ World Concept* [1981/1985] 3rd ed. with Postface (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 2012) 218 & <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14200/14249/>> as well as his ‘The Contemporaneity of Lukács’ Ideas with Modern Social Theoretical Thought: *The Ontology of Social Being* in Social Science Reconstruction with Regards to Constructs like Law’ *Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie* 99 (2013) 1, 42–54 & <http://elib.sfu-kras.ru/bitstream/2311/19820/4/01_Varga.pdf>.

¹¹ Csaba Varga ‘Liberty, Equality, and the Conceptual Minimum of Legal Mediation’ in *Enlightenment, Rights and Revolution* Essays in Legal and Social Philosophy, ed. Neil MacCormick & Zenon Bankowski (Aberdeen: Aberdeen University Press 1989), 229–251 on 247 {reprint in *Marxian Legal Theory* ed. Csaba Varga (Aldershot, Hong Kong, Singapore, Sydney: Dartmouth & New York: The New York University Press 1993) xxvii + 530 [The International Library of Essays in Law & Legal Theory, Schools 9], 501–523 as well as in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14700/14760/>>, 38–61}.

¹² A preliminary issue for whatever comparative study of legal cultures is to identify what the underlying ideal of *ordo* is; cf. note 6.

¹³ Cf. Varga *The Paradigms*.

¹⁴ *Comparative Legal Cultures* ed. Csaba Varga (Aldershot, Hong Kong, Singapore, Sydney: Dartmouth & New York: The New York University Press 1992) xxiv + 614 [The International Library of Essays in Law & Legal Theory, Legal Cultures 1], with a further specimen represented by the *jeito* in Brazil.

In 1917, the revolutionary upheaval in Russia forced Lenin to make huge a number of decisions never thought through in any far-reaching depth.¹⁵ It is to be noted that Marxist revolutionaries in general were rather theory-minded-cum-dogma-driven thinkers who, with the exception of the short-lived Paris Commune, were short of any genuine state-building experience. The leaders of 1917, too, spent their earlier (mostly prison or exile) time by crystallizing their views through live debates. No wonder that “in 1917, when the October Revolution took place, no coherent theory of socialist law had been drafted and was ready to replace the bourgeois law of that day.”¹⁶ What is more, Lenin was by far not interested in the law. In consequence, the opinions he formulated may have been just casual.¹⁷

It is of course rather ironic to remember that, among others, KARL MARX was a law student,¹⁸ GYÖRGY LUKÁCS had a doctorate in *rerum politicarum*,¹⁹ and Lenin, as a law-graduate, practiced law professionally as well.²⁰ According to sources,²¹ at a time when he could hardly foresee other career than lawyering for himself, he only attacked the bar with moral outrage even in routine cases, instead of arguing like a lawyer.²² He may have copied MARX, blind and taciturn

¹⁵ As sources, see V. I. Lenin *Collected Works* 1–45 in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/cw/index.htm>> [in the following: *LCW*] and В. И. Ленин *Полное собрание сочинений* 1–55 Изд. пятое (Москва: Изд. Политической Литературы 1968) in <<http://uaio.ru/vil/vilall.htm>> [in the following: *PSS*].

¹⁶ Pierre Lavigne ‘La légalité socialiste et le développement de la préoccupation juridique en Union Soviétique’ *Revue d’Études Comparatives Est-Ouest* 11 (Septembre 1980) 3, 5–20 on 5: „en 1917, au moment de la Révolution d’Octobre, aucune théorie cohérente de droit socialiste n’avait été élaborée et n’était prêt à substituer au droit bourgeois de la veille.”

¹⁷ Piers Beirne & Alan Hunt ‘Law and the Constitution of Soviet Society: The Case of Comrade Lenin’ *Law & Society Review* 22 (1988) 3, 575–614 on 585 speaks of “the fragmented character of Lenin’s views on a topic that was not among his major concerns”.

¹⁸ At the age of seventeen, he was a law student at Bonn (1835), then in Berlin (1836), but defended his doctoral thesis in philosophy at Jena (1841).

¹⁹ Vö. Varga *The Place of Law*.

²⁰ He began studies at the Kazan law faculty in the autumn of 1886, but fired off, he obtained a license to study in Petrograd, where he got a diploma with excellent mark at the age of twenty-two on January 14, 1892. In Samara he had worked as a clerk for one and a half years until enrolling nominally in Petrograd by autumn 1893 where he devoted himself fully to the political cause, preparing papers and leading debates. А. Н. Трайнин & М. Л. Шифман ‘Страницы из биографии В. И. Ленина’ [Pages from Lenin’s biography] *Советское государство и право* 1956/3, 61–71 [A. N. Trainin & M. L. Shifman ‘Stranitsy iz biografii V. I. Lenina’ *Sovetskoe gosudarstvo i pravo*], quoted by Jane Burbank ‘Lenin and the Law in Revolutionary Russia’ *Slavic Review* 54 (1995) 1, 23–44 on 25. A more complete bibliography is offered by ‘»Библиотека юридических редкостей«, раздел посвященный юридической деятельности В. И. Ленина’ <<https://yroslav1985.livejournal.com/124890.html>>.)

²¹ Twenty-four cases are documented from Samara in В. И. Ленин *Неизвестные документы* [Unknown documents] 1891–1922, ред. Ю. Н. Амиантов и др. (Москва: Росспэн 1999; 2018) 670, 18. [V. I. Lenin *Neizvestnye dokumenty*, ed. Yuriy Nikolaevich Amiantov et al. (Moscow: Rosspen)].

²² Lenin kept an “unequivocally hostile” impress of the entire profession, perhaps as an imprint of his failure in lawyering; cf. Eugene Huskey *Russian Lawyers and the Soviet State The Origins and Development of the Soviet Bar, 1917–1989* (Princeton: Princeton University Press 1986) xii + 247 at 37–38. According to Tamás Krausz *Reconstructing Lenin An Intellectual Biography*, trans. Bálint Bethlenfalvy (New York: Monthly Review Press 2015) 552 & <<https://rosswolfe.files.wordpress.com/2015/02/tamacc81s-krausz-reconstructing-lenin-an-intellectual-biography.pdf>> at 36–37, “He would not have become a good lawyer as his guiding principles were social, guided by ethical laws, and formed all of his decisions from the perspective of the economically downtrodden.” All that notwithstanding, his temporary status in January changed to permanent assistant barrister

in issues of law,²³ who “appears predisposed simply to ignore the question of law as peripheral [...]. MARX’s jurisprudential thought is often premised upon a critique of law *per se*, and what he has to say tends to be overwhelmingly negative in character.”²⁴

In addition, there was also a hint in doctrinal grounding which, albeit it could have also initiated new and truly theoretical—ontological—research directions, served only to base devastating consequences in a politically driven environment. For

“Nor did the writings of MARX and ENGELS seem to offer much beyond a paralyzing legal nihilism. [...] The nihilism of this confused vacuum was exacerbated by the view, forcefully insisted to by ENGELS, that because law was the *world view* of the bourgeoisie it was only the most backward sections of the socialist movement that voiced their demands in legalistic terms.”²⁵

Was it rejection? Or simply nihilization? I guess there’s much more to it. Its message was repeated as a commonplace by Soviet-Russian theorists as Lenin’s contemporaries: “Religion and law are the ideologies of the suppressing classes, the latter gradually replacing the former.”²⁶ Rephrased as a political agenda, by degrading law to mere ideology something more than simple ontological reconstruction has taken place. For thousands of years, law has served as the supreme factor of social integration, a constant expression of the latter’s products and changing states.²⁷ And by the fact that the new Soviet law and legal ideology based upon arbitrary repression while throwing back a most important pillar of mankind’s second nature into the ethereal realm of illusions, the very

by July. It is to be added, however, that it was his chess partner in the office of whom he worked. Cf. Robert Service *Lenin A Political Life*, 1 (Houndmills & London: Macmillan 1985) viii + 246 on 46.

²³ As to G. B. Smith ‘Socialist Legality and Legal Policy in the Soviet Union’ in *Public Policy and Administration in the Soviet Union* ed. G. B. Smith (New York: Praeger 1980), 109–141 on 111, „the writings of MARX and ENGELS provided LENIN only scant guidelines to follow in constructing a socialist state. MARX was foremost a social critic, not an architect of a new economic and political order that he predicted.”

²⁴ Andrew Vincent ‘Marx and Law’ *Journal of Law and Society* 20 (1993) 4, 371–397 on 371.

²⁵ Piers Beirne ‘Editor’s Introduction’ in *Revolution in Law Contributions to the Development of Soviet Legal Theory, 1917–1938*, ed. Piers Beirne (New York: Routledge 1990), i–xiv at ix–x.

²⁶ By Aleksandr Grigorievich Goichbarg, *Foundations of the Private Property Law* [А. Г. Гойхбарг *Основы частного имущественного права* (Очерки) (Москва: Красная новь 1924) 136] in <<https://thecharnelhouse.org/2016/04/14/marxism-and-legal-theory/>> and *Economic Law* [А. Г. Гойхбарг *Хозяйственное право П.С.Ф.С.Р.* I: Гражданский кодекс, 3-е изд. (Москва: Государственное издательство 1924) 19 [Учебники и учебные пособия для вузов]] on 8 —, quoted by Vladimir Gsovski ‘The Soviet Concept of Law’ *Fordham Law Review* VII (1938) 1, 1–44 on 12.

²⁷ It is the task of ontological reconstruction to answer what is capable of “binding” or “obliging” in the law. For law as the aggregate of official expectations (i.e. normative texts) is, in and by itself, apparently nothing more than a dead item. But law also appears as fact, in the practice of special state machineries established for that their fulfillment will be guaranteed. So the genuine issue is in what manner law can serve as one of the pillars of social integration. Inquiries into linguistic normativities have once emerged from the Nordic skepticism about German normativism [*Begriffsjurisprudenz*], formally self-closing. Cf., e.g., Varga Csaba ‘Skandináv jogi realizmus’ [Scandinavian legal realism] in *Jogbölcsélet XIX–XX. század, Előadások, szerk. Varga Csaba* (Budapest: Szent István Társulat 1999), 81–91 [Bibliotheca Cathedrae Philosophiae Iuris et Rerum Politicarum Universitatis Catholicae de Petro Pázmány nominatae].

civilizing vocation, and force, of the law itself was annulled. Or, as a Bolshevik from Hungary described it, waiting for a revolutionary revival after the fall of the Hungarian Soviet Republic: by freeing themselves mentally from the bourgeois spell of »the law«, revolutionaries will disengage from its psychical effect. For, thereby he only stated: effects conventionalized come from inside, from consciousness, formed or deformed for being able to trigger exactly such effect.²⁸

The MARXist tradition of depreciating the law as an accessory phenomenon, having but circumstantial and derivate importance, has manifested on three levels: one, as a hothouse of the almost anarchist nihilization of law; two, the law's degradation into an entity that can be easily turned into a simplest carrier of communication; and three, as a background factor by the force of which they blocked their way to the idea of strategic planning and acting. In fact, law was rather used occasionally, now and then just for posteriorly repairing randomly produced dysfunctionalities.²⁹

All in all, Lenin's occasional opinions³⁰ cannot be regarded as parts of an overall theory; they are rather *hic et nunc* directives by a leader on duty. In general, "Lenin's views on law [...] appear [...] as weapons [...] in the service of particular aims [...] from different wars and different epochs of combat technology."³¹

²⁸ George Lukács 'Legality and Illegality' (July 1920) in George Lukács *History and Class Consciousness Studies in Marxist Dialectics*, trans. Rodney Livingstone (Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press [1968]), 256–270 on 263 and cf. also Varga *The Place of Law*, 45: "Where the total, communist fearlessness with regard to the state and the law is present, the law and its calculable consequences are of no greater (if also of no smaller) importance than any other external fact of life with which it is necessary to reckon when deciding upon any definitive course of action. The risk of breaking the law should not be regarded any differently than the risk of missing a train connection when on an important journey."

This ontological recognition has not inspired any specific research with the exception of a Hungarian in Sydney, who separated a "systematic-explanatory" variation in the understanding of ideology, answering the issue of "how the ideas of the ruling class »normally« rule the whole of society". According to his definition, "Institutionally disseminated systems of ruling ideas are seen by MARX to systematize the confused and chaotic conceptions of everyday thinking, to lend a degree of logical coherence to their fragmented structure, to explain away (and thereby apologize for) the most widely encountered experiences that contradict the seeming self-evidence of fetishistic categories." György Márkus 'Concepts of Ideology in Marx' *Canadian Journal of Political and Social Theory* 15 (1991) 1–2 & 3 [15th Anniversary Issue: »Ideology and Power in the Age of Lenin in Ruins«], 87–106 & <<http://mmduvic.ca/index.php/ctheory/article/download/14271/5046>> on 93. The investigation into »law as ideology«, carried out by the Critical Legal Studies movement (an off-spring of US 1968), has reduced itself to superficial MARXian ideology-critical reconstructionism, what Márkus may call the ideology's "unmasking" meaning. See, e.g., Paul Hirst *On Law and Ideology* (London: Macmillan 1979) vii + 181 [Language, Discourse, Society] and Valerie Kerruish *Jurisprudence as Ideology* (London: Routledge 1992) xii + 221 [Sociology of Law and Crime].

²⁹ For instance, neither Thomas Bell *A Dictionary of Terms and Quotations* Compiled from the Works of V. I. Lenin (London: Lawrence & Wishart 1942) 44 [Little Lenin Library 25] nor Anton Pannekoek *Lenin as Philosopher A Critical Examination of the Philosophical Basis of Leninism [1938/1948]* rev. ed. (Marquette University Press 2003) 177 [Marquette Studies in Philosophy] find any legal relevance in Lenin's oeuvre.

³⁰ Treated in term of legal techniques used by Lenin, see Csaba Varga 'Lenin and Revolutionary Law-making' {originally prepared to the volume *В. И. Ленин о социалистическом государстве и праве* (note 82), 271–280} *International Review of Contemporary Law* [Brussels] 1982/1, 47–59 {reprint in *Comparative Legal Cultures* ed. Varga, 515–527}.

³¹ Burbank, Abstract.

At a time when “class struggle” became the rallying call—a personal *raison d'être*—for Lenin, he already anticipated the application of whatever instrument, illegal or legal.³² The target was first “the bureaucracy”—meaning czarist state and law—, and from 1905 onwards, “the bourgeois legality”.³³ In his fight against rivalling Liberals and Social Democrats, he stressed thereby that ‘law’ as such should not be fetishized, moreover, Russia had no kind of ‘law’ that could be the analogon of the one in the bourgeois world, widely accepted by the public as the basis of social cohesion. Or, the western prestige of law should not be transposed into what was no more than the „omnipotence of the bureaucracy”.³⁴ Otherwise speaking, Lenin did never reckon with the potential of such an unbeatable force of all-social integration for Russia; for him, law had always a negative, interventionist and repressive sense, far away from any readiness for protection. Again, by December 1911, bureaucracy and police were named repeatedly as the targeted enemy.³⁵ When in summer-end of 1917 he escaped to Finland and wrote *The State and Revolution*, he promised the “complete destruction of the bureaucracy”.³⁶ One or two months before the October putsch, he only envisaged “direct class struggle” at a time when the Mensheviks and Social Revolutionaries fought, by means of law, for that the Constituent Assembly would be convened, for that—*horribile dictu*, as Lenin promptly alarmed—they can issue laws, that is, submerging again in legal activity.³⁷

An author opines that

“Given this situation of theoretical unpreparedness for unexpected practical experience with power the revolutionaries were faced with a dilemma. They were confronted with the choice of either »no-law« i.e. more violent anarchy which would lead them to being accused of irresponsibility and nihilism or of trying to adapt the bourgeois law to the socialist ends and be accused of revisionism, degeneracy, reformism or boot-licking.”³⁸

³² E.g., Lenin *What Is to Be Done?* in *LCW* 5, 349–529 at 454–467. From the time Lenin decided so, he kept the two together: “The party of the working class [...] must combine legal with illegal work” Lenin ‘The Political Situation: Four Theses’ (July 10/23, 1917) in *LCW* 25, 180 <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/cw/pdf/lenin-cw-vol-25.pdf>>.

³³ Cf. Burbank, 26–29, and particularly 29, note 25. The list of ‘enemy’ targets is enriched when, e.g. in the fall of 1914, he criticises the opportunists “by making a fetish of the necessary utilization of bourgeois parliamentarianism and bourgeois legality, and forgetting that illegal forms of organisation and propaganda are imperative at times of crises.” Lenin ‘The War and Russian Social-Democracy’ (November 1, 1914) in *LCW* 21, 25–34 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1914/sep/28.htm>>.

³⁴ Lenin ‘Три запроса’ [‘Tri zaprosa’] (December 1911) in *PSS* 21 & <<http://uaio.ru/vil/21.htm>>, 104–116 on 115.

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ Lenin ‘Государство и революция’ (1917) in *PSS* 33 & <<http://uaio.ru/vil/33.htm>>, 1–120 on 117.

³⁷ Lenin ‘Constitutional Illusions’ (July 26/August 8) in *LCW* 25 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1917/jul/26.htm>>, 196–197: „The Mensheviks and Socialist-Revolutionaries laid emphasis on the act of law: the proclamation, the promise, the declaration to call a Constituent Assembly. The Bolsheviks laid emphasis on the class struggle”.

³⁸ Eric Allen Engle ‘Socialist Legalism in the Early USSR: A Formal Rule of Law State?’ in his *Marxism, Liberalism, and Feminism* Leftist Legal Thought (New Delhi: Serials Publications 2010), 44–64, quoted from <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=1268555>> (2008) 17 on 3.

Of course, such dilemmas and post-inventions are mostly artificial. Was Lenin pondering in such niceties at all? Or was he prejudiced as a MARXist from the very beginnings? Nearly fifteen to twenty thousand printed pages are what he produced in texts, and no passage of these can be taken as alluding to the former assumption.

Let's see one talkative example! He is not aware in Finland that within some weeks his revolution will break out in Petrograd. In his *The State and Revolution* program he circumscribes the specimen of state the proletariat needs: “only a state which is withering away, i.e., a state so constituted that it begins to wither away immediately, and cannot but wither away.”, or, a state “which is »no longer a state in the proper sense of the word«”;³⁹ for, in Bolshevism, the state is not abolished but made proletarian and gradually self-administered.⁴⁰

So, what will have happened from the moment when—according to the symbolism of a liar mystification⁴¹—the Aurora's long tom trembles, signaling that a new world would be born?

Lenin was to prepare such a moment through all his life. Nearly fifty years old, captive of the idea of how to destroy czarism and build a communist society. Anyone in St. Petersburg walking to the Peter and Paul Fortress' Trubeckoy Bastion prison can revive the true lives of those dreaming day and night, nurturing one-cause fixed by their single mind: how to transcend human suffering in a long desired but never reached earthly heavens. PLEKHANOV may have resounded to this ultimate issue by his credo: “*salus populi suprema lex – salus revolutionis suprema lex.*”⁴² Thereby whatever tool promising the goal is sanctified.

³⁹ <<https://www.marxists.org/ebooks/lenin/state-and-revolution.pdf>>, II/1 and V/4.

⁴⁰ It is worth recalling that the writings of devoted revolutionaries like Lenin were part of doctrinarians' constant debate to identify the gist of “the Teaching”. Therefore even their semblances to pure philosophising may be without merits in scholarship. At the same time, their direct political function may explain (if certainly not justify) the harshness of Lenin's language use, his reflexly offensive and humiliatory criticism with destroying overtones; cf., e.g., E. M. Рыт Ленин о языке и язык Ленина [Lenin on language and Lenin's language] (Москва: ГосЛитИздат 1936) 135. In any case, the subtitle of *The State and Revolution* is »The Marxist Theory of the State & the Tasks of the Proletariat in the Revolution«—that is, treating the state figures not as a text-book subject but stands for what the subtitle's second part will impute to it.

In political pragmatism, subject to the success of practice, everything is a function of changing situations. Debates are held in search for most pragmatic answers. Situationality explains why diverse emphases and apparently contradictory statements may be drawn from given texts. In a sense, as a common feature of political ideologies taken as rigidified -isms, the varying paths of Soviet legal theorising were repeatedly concluded from selected Leninist answers in a relative disregard to his others. Cf. Ivo Lapenna *State and Law Soviet and Yugoslav Theory* (London: University of London / The Athlone Press 1964) xi + 135, in particular 27–42.

⁴¹ Sořia Sávina ‘Aurora: The Cruiser that Sparked a Revolution – Or did it?’ *Russia Beyond* (November 07, 2014)

<https://www.rbth.com/arts/2014/11/07/aurora_the_cruiser_that_sparked_a_revolution_or_did_it_41229.html>.

⁴² “[T]he success of the revolution is the highest law. If it were necessary for the success of the revolution to restrict the affect of one or another democratic principle, it would be criminal to stop at such a restriction.”—as opined by PLEKHANOV at the Second Party Congress of the Russian Social-Democrats, framing their programme in 1903. [„успех революции – высший закон. И если бы ради успеха революции потребовалось временно ограничить действие того или другого демократического принципа, то перед таким ограничением преступно было бы останавливаться.”] *Протоколы второго съезда партии*, 168–169, quoted by Lenin for

How did the liquidators of czarism start building this Golden Age revenant?

3. The Events

On the first four hundred days, 1,033 decrees, proclamations and the like were issued, and 596 in the next year.⁴³ Of these, Lenin formulated the Decree on Peace, the Decree on Land, the Proposal on Workers' Control, the Decree on the Dissolution of the Constitutional Assembly, as well as the Declaration of the Rights of the Working and Exploited People.⁴⁴ The first two were launched by the Second All-Russia Congress of Soviets of Workers' and Soldiers Deputies on the first day of the revolution, and issued the next day with hope to „pacify and satisfy” amidst “economic chaos and a peasant revolt”.⁴⁵ What may have been its genuine purpose? In today's reconstruction, it was to draw the peasantry to the revolutionaries' side; to overthrow the old establishment through abolishing land ownership; and to make the peasantry an active part for the revolution.⁴⁶ The instrument⁴⁷ was a simple legal form, imitating normative contents. However, driven by radical enthusiasm for the force of mobilization, all it⁴⁸ was drafted in form of declaration, entrusting the selection of subjects and methods (of who and how to act) to arbitrary local initiative, while acknowledging any final (random) by the seal of law. To this, only empty rhetoric could add the complimentary (perhaps sheerly cynical) confidence that the denouement, all that notwithstanding, would be self-balancing.⁴⁹ Practically

its actualisation in *Pravda* (December 22, 1917) 221, reprinted in *PSS* 35, 185 & <<http://uaio.ru/vil/35.htm#s510>>, resp. in *LCW* 42 at 47–49 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1917/dec/23.htm>>.

⁴³ *Сборник декретов...* [Collection of decrees] (Москва: Гос. изд-во 1920-[1921]) [Собрание узаконений и распоряжений рабоче-крестьянского правительства].

“[S]ome, such as *On Combating the Famine* and *To the Population*, had no legal status”. Beirne & Hunt, 589. Cf. also (November 5, 1917) in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1917/nov/05.htm>> and (January 14, 1918) in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1918/jan/14.htm>>.

⁴⁴ Beirne & Hunt, 595.

⁴⁵ Indeed, 150,000,000 hectares of land were added to peasant-used lands, and the equivalent of 800 Gold Rubles per annum leased lands became free; cf. *Страна Советов за 50 лет* [Half a century of the country of soviets] Сборник стат. материалов (Москва: Статистика 1967) 351, 115 [*Strana Sovetov za 50 let* (Moscow: Statistika)], quoted by N. D. Kazantsev ‘From Lenin's 1917 Decree on the Land to the Principles of Land Legislation’ *Soviet Law and Government* VII (1969) 4, 3–12 on 5.

⁴⁶ As recalled on October 31, 1922, this, “unlike any other laws, [...] though very imperfect from the technical and perhaps also from the juridical point of view, nevertheless, provided the peasants with all that was vital and essential for them, and ensured their alliance with the workers.” Lenin in *LCW* 45 in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1922/oct/31.htm>>.

⁴⁷ Jared T. McKeon ‘Bolsheviks' Decree on the Land Quells Peasant Unrest' (March 5, 2013) <<http://web.mit.edu/russia1917/papers/1026-BolsheviksDecreeOnLandQuellsPeasants.pdf>>, 3–4: “successful in answering the peasants' land question, which in turn helped the Bolsheviks acquire peasant support in the winter of 1917–1918.”

⁴⁸ “A single decree putting an end to landed proprietorship will win us the confidence of the peasantry”. Lenin ‘Meeting of the Petrograd Soviet of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies' (October 25/November 7, 1917) in *LCW* 26, 239–241 on 240 <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1917/oct/25a.htm>>.

⁴⁹ Lenin ‘Report on Land' at the Second All-Russia Congress of Soviets of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies (October 26/November 8, 1917) in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1917/oct/25-26/26d.htm>>.

the law had no genuine ordering content. It meant that a decisive step of the overall socio-economic transformation was entrusted to mere spontaneity, to the variety of local devotees' wanton choices. Law ordered the law's silence on the issue. Lenin was open at the All-Russian Congress: to instigate the masses to engage themselves in local rebellions, a sphere of freedom for action was to be secured, only hoping the good effect. Most importantly to him, "the peasants should be firmly assured that there are no more landowners in the countryside, that they themselves must decide all questions, and that they themselves must arrange their own lives." This is why he had to nurture "the general stream of revolutionary creative work": "We must be guided by experience; we must allow complete freedom to the creative faculties of the masses."⁵⁰

In the wake of such a course of action the dual drive by issuing decrees (for propaganda, agitation, mobilization) while preserving sheer arbitrariness (whenever it could help the cause)⁵¹ began its spectacular career. Doubts may have arisen but never on behalf of Lenin; all this was of paramount importance to him.⁵²

Lenin's posterior self-evaluation simultaneously reaffirmed and impoverished this choice: thereby they completely lost sight of the future, blocking their own path promising some established legal culture.

„If we had expected that life in the rural districts could be completely changed by writing a hundred decrees, we would have been absolute idiots. But if we had refrained from indicating in decrees the road that must be followed, we would have been traitors to socialism. These decrees, while in practice they could not be carried into effect fully and immediately, played an important part as propaganda. [...]

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ Ivo Lapenna 'Lenin, Law and Legality' in *Lenin: The Man, the Theorist, the Leader A Reappraisal*, ed. Leonard Schapiro & Peter Reddaway (New York: Praeger 1967), 235–264 on 250: "issued mainly for propaganda purposes". Engle, 4: "Hortatory proclamations declaring guidelines and objectives were the rule." Beirne & Hunt, 577 & 589: "a minor but nevertheless useful educative vehicle" "issued largely for purposes of education and propaganda". Sensitively reconsidered, Robert Service *Lenin A Political Life*, 2 (Houndmills & London: Macmillan 1991) xviii + 422 on 282 thinks that "The laws were instruments of agitation and propaganda; they displayed a commitment to revolution at all costs which spilled over into legal nihilism."

According to Beirne & Hunt, 589–595, "eradication / education / discipline / transition / participation / routinization (accounting and control)" were the functions Lenin expected law should fulfill.

⁵² Михаил Павлович Ирошников *Создание советского центрального государственного аппарата* [Foundation of the Soviet central state apparatus] Совет Нар. Комиссаров и нар. комиссариаты (Окт. 1917 г. – янв. 1918 г.) 2-е изд. (Ленинград: Наука 1967) 302 on 120 [M. P. Iroshnikov *Sozdanie sovetского tseentralizovannogo gosudarstvennogo apparata* Sovet narodnykh komissarov i narodnye komissariaty (Leningrad: Nauka)] recalls Lenin remembering that in want of "a form of propaganda", we "would not be able to occupy leading positions". The (later executed) agricultural scientist VALERIAN OBOLENSKY-OSSINSKY made a personal reservation indeed; but when forced to withdraw this, after all he stated: "At the moment of a massive assault on the capital, it is necessary to declare a goal, in the form of a decree, toward which the masses should strive." Николай Осинский [pen name] 'Из первых дней Высшего совета народного хозяйства' [From the first days of the Supreme Soviet of national farming] [Nikolai Osinskii 'Iz pervykh dnei Vysshego soveta narodnogo khoziaistva' Narodnoe khoziaistvo] *Народное хозяйство* 1918/11, 14. Both quotes from Tatiana Iu. Borisova 'The Legitimacy of the Bolshevik Order, 1917–1918: Language Usage in Revolutionary Russian Law' *Review of Central and East European Law* 37 (2012), 395–419 on 403.

Decrees are instructions which call for practical work on a mass scale.”

That is, decrees served as a call for massive arbitrariness, covered by legal form. In the absence of normative contents, there remained nothing in them to execute in a behavior-regulating sense. From their practice, however, enormous experience could be accumulated over time. “If we treat matters in this way we shall acquire a good deal from the sum total of our laws, decrees, and ordinances. We shall not regard them as absolute injunctions which must be put into effect instantly and at all costs.”⁵³

All in all, such a decree-issuing, instead of canalizing, only launches legal processes. By its speech craft of calling to action, it is momentary and contentless. The legal authority it provides is a mere framework, with the arbitrary practice it will generate filling in. Its logic is undefined generality in terms of law and random variations in reality produced. Lenin emphasized whilst launching it:

“We want no details in [this draft law], for we are writing a decree, not a programme of action. Russia is vast, and local conditions vary. We trust that the peasants themselves will be able to solve the problem correctly, properly, better than we could do it.”

Ten days later he continued:

“our draft law is not perfect. But it will be applied everywhere by the Soviets in accordance with their local conditions. We are not bureaucrats and do not want to insist on the letter of the law everywhere, as was the practice in the old government offices. [...] The local Soviets, depending on time and place, can amend, enlarge and add to the basic provisions worked out by the government. Creative activity at the grass roots is the basic factor of the new public life”.⁵⁴

Soon, however, genuine institutional arrangements, too, had to be made. First of them was the renewal of courts, in the course of which “We transformed the court from an instrument of exploitation into an instrument of education”.⁵⁵ Three decrees they dedicated to it, serving continuity and revolution at the same time. For the time being, the old professional staff was taken over with reference allowed to old rules whilst it also encouraged measures of revolutionary

⁵³ Lenin ‘Report on the Work in the Countryside’ (1919. március 23.) in *LCW* 29, 141–225 on 209 & in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/cw/pdf/lenin-cw-vol-29.pdf>>.

⁵⁴ By Lenin, ‘Report on Land’ (October 26/November 8, 1917) in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1917/oct/25-26/26d.htm>> as well as ‘Meeting of the All-Russia Central Executive Committee’ (November 4/17, 1917) in *LCW* 26, 284–292 on 285 & 287–288 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1917/nov/04a.htm>>, [2].

⁵⁵ Lenin ‘Third All-Russia Congress of Soviets of Workers’, Soldiers’ and Peasants’ Deputies’ (14/24 January, 1918) in *LCW* 26, 453–482 on 464 & in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1918/jan/10.htm>>.

justice.⁵⁶ The target Lenin set to these old-new tribunals was to “enforce the will of the proletariat, apply its decrees, and in the absence of a suitable decree, or if the relevant decree is inadequate, take guidance from your socialist sense of justice, ignoring the laws of the deposed governments.”⁵⁷

Regarding law, a full bazaar from various angers, experiences, and doctrinal stands seethed in Lenin’s mind. In what they were common was exclusively the denial of the very idea of right and the cynical anarchism of “the end justifies the means”. Heralding the communitarian self-management of Communism in the movement’s Utopianism,⁵⁸ the tenet of “every citizen is a judge” became a party program by early 1919, saying that “anybody can act as a judge basing himself on the revolutionary sense of justice of the working class”.⁵⁹ The tenet of popular participation applied to public administration as well.⁶⁰

Additionally further tasks emerged, too, and law-related dysfunctions had also to be somewhat cured. Such challenge was to stop the laws’ proliferation; to build “uniform legality” out of the chaos produced by the concurrence of regulatory bodies; and to force back mob-terror (an associate by-product of the “revolutionary sense of justice”) into the bottle of “discipline and observance of the law”.

Lenin’s actions, predominantly power-driven,⁶¹ alternated between the extremes. As already mentioned, in 1918, when the Bolsheviks fought for that

⁵⁶ Analysing the three decrees (issued on November 24, 1917; February 2, 1918; July 20, 1918, respectively), see Aaron B. Retish ‘The Revolutionary Courts’ <<https://cpb-us-w2.wpmucdn.com/u.osu.edu/dist/a/49661/files/2017/10/Revolutionary-Courts-OSU-Retish-2jskdqa.pdf>>, who emphasises their reorganising effect favourable to transition, instead of any disorganisation.

⁵⁷ Ibid. Similarly, the Decree on Abolition of Existing Legal Institutions [in *Собрание узаконений и распоряжений рабоче-крестьянского правительства* 1917/4, 49–51 <<https://www.marxists.org/history/ussr/events/revolution/documents/1917/11/24.htm>>] stipulates also that “Local courts [...] will be guided [...] by the laws of the deposed governments only in so far as those laws have not been annulled by the revolution and do not contradict the revolutionary conscience and the revolutionary conceptions of right.” Cf. also Lenin ‘Draft Programme of the R.C.P.(B.)’ (March 18–23, 1919) in *LCW* 29, 97–140 on 131 resp. <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1919/mar/x02.htm>>, [8].

⁵⁸ Cf., e.g., Csaba Varga ‘Utopias of Rationality in the Development of the Idea of Codification’ *Rivista Internazionale di Filosofia del Diritto* LV (1978) 1, 21–38 & in *Law and the Future of Society* ed. F. C. Hutley, Eugene Kamenka & Alice Erh–Soon Tay (Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner Verlag 1979), 27–41 [Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie, Beiheft 11] {reprint in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/14200/14231/>>, Part Two, Ch. X, Para. 3}.

⁵⁹ Lenin *Eighth Congress of the R.C.P.(B.)* in *LCW* 29, 182.

⁶⁰ Lenin *The State and Revolution* in *LCW* 25, 381–492, 420–421: modern capitalism “has created large-scale production, factories, railways, the postal service, telephone, etc., and on this basis the great majority of the functions of the old »state power« have become so simplified and can be reduced to such exceedingly simple operations of registration, filing and checking that they can be easily performed by every literate person”. Similarly Lenin ‘The Immediate Tasks of the Soviet Government’ (April 30, 1918) in *LCW* 27, 235–277 at 272–273: “for the first time a start is made by the entire population in learning the art of administration [...] our aim is to ensure that every toiler, having finished his eight hour »task« in productive labour shall perform state duties without pay.”

⁶¹ Stephen J. Lee *Lenin and Revolutionary Russia* (London: Routledge 2003) xv + 153 [Questions and Analysis in History] on 97 resp. 111 opines on the decrees *On Land* resp. *On Workers’ Control* (October 27, 1917) and their relative loneliness that they may have fruited from intuition, “broadly representing the wishes of most of the people”. For “Lenin had no economic strategy at all; rather the economic changes were connected with the political situation in which Lenin found himself at a particular time. There was therefore a strong element of pragmatism [...], and his economic policies were again conditioned by considerations of power.”

they could gain unrestricted power of decree-issuing, Lenin openly trespassed common platform by refusing alleged “bourgeois formalism” (seconded by LEON TROTZKY, who referred to the situational inadequacy of any “conventional parliamentary machinery”).⁶² However, in a little while they had to manage their uncontrollably increased decree-issuing production—arranging them with necessary changes made.⁶³

Having a look at Russia’s impressive territorial size, “the spontaneous anarchism of the population, which the Bolsheviks did their utmost to encourage” disintegrated this vast country; practically by June 1918 it fell to pieces (akin to once feudal particularism) and originated “at least thirty-three sovereign »governments«”, “a realm of self-governing principalities”.⁶⁴ An opposition Socialist, emigrating already by 1919, characterizes this new fragmentation by a “chaotic pile-up of organs [...] with the natural desire of each of them to be higher than all the rest [...]. Everyone gives orders, and no one carries any orders out.”⁶⁵ The chaos of momentary actions/reactions must have split even the elementary tissues of social cohesion. And the pragmatism of forced success, heated by destructive spirit, ended in “violent lawlessness”, in consequence of which “law broke down and the rule of force became the norm”.⁶⁶

One of the feasible interpretations approaches the subject by analyzing the use of language. It concludes to two stages, mostly in succession. The first is the period of revolutionary decrees, addressed to the people. In order to mobilize them for purposeful free action, decrees legitimized both the course and the results of the project—in addition to legitimizing the revolution itself. A couple of months later, the *propaganda* language of the former was replaced by *bureaucratic* language, becoming exclusive by March 1918. Addressed to local Soviets formed in the meantime, they returned to the use of the old, pre-revolutionary professional style.⁶⁷ But the perplexing question remains, raised

Or, in the end, Lenin worded the NAPOLEONIC apocrypha as the only way when you are on a path without alternatives: „On s’engage et puis... on voit”. Lenin ‘Our Revolution’ (January 16, 1923) in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1923/jan/16.htm>>; cf. also <<https://history.stackexchange.com/questions/9396/did-napoleon-ever-say-on-sengage-et-puis-on-voit?rq=1>>.

⁶² Richard Pipes *A Concise History of the Russian Revolution* [1995] (New York: Vintage Books 1996) xix + 431 at 154–156.

⁶³ Lenin ‘Fifth All-Russia Congress of Soviets of Workers’, Peasants’, Soldiers’ and Red Army Deputies’ (July 4–10, 1918) in *LCW* 27, 505–532 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1918/jul/04.htm>> on 519: “But be is a poor revolutionary who at a time of acute struggle is halted by the immutability of a law. In a period of transition laws have only a temporary validity; and when a law hinders the development of the revolution, it must be abolished or amended.”

⁶⁴ Pipes, 152, 154 & 153.

⁶⁵ Марк Вениаминович Вишняк *Большевизм и демократия* [Bol’shevizm i demokratiia] [Bolshevism and democracy] (New York: Narodopravstvo 1919) 36, 9, quoted by Jane Burbank *Intelligentsia and Revolution Russian Views of Bolshevism, 1917–1922* (New York & Oxford: Oxford University Press 1986) viii + 340 on 88. (It is interesting to note that the author, Mark Vedianimovich Vishniak, at a later time became Richard Pipes’ master at Cornell University.)

⁶⁶ Engle, 4.

⁶⁷ Borisova, 403–406.

by another research, whether or not the spirit of anarchy, freed from the bottle and then only superficially closed back, was to ease the path paved toward lasting totalitarianism.⁶⁸

In the turmoil of revolutionary events, there was plenty of place for political maneuvering. However, by 1922, civil war with strikes, famine and unemployment amounted to risking anyone's very survival. Marching through chaos had to end: "»*The phase of propaganda by decrees*« is over".⁶⁹ Some legality was to be launched by Lenin between licentious total anarchy and "bourgeois formalism". What is more, it was preceded by his demand from the judiciary "to ensure the strictest discipline and self-discipline of the working people", considering the fact that "the courts are an instrument for inculcating discipline".⁷⁰ But as a security check, all elements of "informality, flexibility, and the explicit dominance of political objectives"⁷¹ were in parallel preserved within this legality.⁷²

In sum, Lenin did not base law simply on rules, on the contemporary European tradition of statutory positivism. Instead, he merged law into revolutionary expediency, that is, into the changing reactions to changing demands of the day's political constellation. In never ceasing terror practice, this resulted in demoralization and the fall of efficiency of the administration, as well as the transfer of responsibility to be taken for decision-making. By fear of retaliation amidst unestablished criteria used in control, the chaos engendered by the self-emptying of competences became the prime motive of deliberation whether or not to act at all.⁷³

Shortly they had to decree, too, that law was law so it was to be obeyed, with the conclusion that everything tried and nothing proven sufficient. With age-old

⁶⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Soviet_Decree>.

⁶⁹ Lenin 'Notes for a Speech on March 27, 1922' in *LCW* 36, 571–575 on 574 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1922/mar/26.htm>>, para. 14 and 16.

Lenin's Decrees on Peace, on Land, and on Workers' Control were launched at the optimum moment to ensure maximum social support. "These three decrees had a key importance in the strategy of the Bolshevik party. They helped it come to power by promising to the people those things which were most urgently desired at the time and which they had been denied by the previous government. [...] The decrees also legitimized the new government and consolidated it in power. The reckoning was that anyone who dared try to overthrow the government which had promulgated these decrees would have to face the wrath of the overwhelming majority of the population." James D. White *Lenin The Practice and Theory of Revolution* (Houndmills & New York: Palgrave Macmillan 2001) x + 262 [European History in Perspective] on 149.

⁷⁰ Lenin 'Original Version of the Article »The Immediate Tasks of the Soviet Government«' (March 28, 1918) in *LCW* 27 & <http://www.marx2mao.com/PDFs/Lenin_CW-Vol.27.pdf>, 203–218 on 217 as well as Lenin 'The Immediate Tasks of the Soviet Government' (March–April 1918) in *LCW* 27, 235–277 on 266.

⁷¹ Beirne & Hunt, 578.

⁷² E.g., by Lenin, 'Meeting of the Petrograd Soviet of Workers' and Soldiers' Deputies' in *LCW* 26, 239–241 on 241; 'Letter to the Workers and Peasants Apropos of the Victory over Kolchak' in *LCW* 29, 552–560 on 556; 'On the Tasks of the People's Commissariat for Justice Under the New Economic Policy' in *LCW* 36, 560–565 on 562.

⁷³ Cf., e.g., T. H. Rigby *Lenin's Government Sovnarkom, 1917–1922* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 1979) and George Leggett *The Cheka Lenin's Political Police: The All-Russian Extraordinary Commission for Combating Counter-Revolution and Sabotage (From December 1917 to February 1922)* (Oxford: Clarendon Press 1981).

bureaucratic routine,⁷⁴ the remedy they found was the inspector inspected.⁷⁵ As secondary effects of failures, such medications soon failed themselves.⁷⁶

In every place and age one of the greatest problem is how to guarantee and constantly guard the unity of law.⁷⁷ As already stated, in Soviet Russia even the least of the sense of communality tore already apart: can the sense of law evolve at all when one is free to live in uncensored arbitrariness? By May 1922, as the most serious defect, Lenin identified the disunity of law having fallen to “Kaluga or Kazan law”, and instituted special prosecutorial oversight for that “uniform all-Russian law” could eventually rule, the minimum of a well-organized state.⁷⁸

According to one interpretation,⁷⁹ the first month “anti-bureaucratism” (calling for mass actions) passed into “anti-formalism” (fearful of losing on confrontations within the Constitutional Assembly) from December 1917 on.⁸⁰ Within the span of some months, general famine ensued. Lenin may have started realizing how his destructive Utopias made a whole society defenseless. As a prayer wheel, rigidifying in want of anything better, now he put again the “major real task—administration, organization and supervision” on the active agenda; looked for “more exact juridical formulations”; moreover, from

⁷⁴ So what shall be Lenin’s “final cure” of the dysfunctions of bureaucracy? More “bureaucracy” – built on itself. Leszek Kolakowski *Main Currents of Marxism Its Rise, Growth, and Dissolution*, 2 (Oxford: Clarendon Press 1978) ix + 542 on 490. In fact, it was an organ super-super-controlling the organs of super-control, headed, by the way, by STALIN, who immediately started using it to build his personal power.

⁷⁵ Cf., as contrasted to the above Lenin ‘Notes for a Speech on March 27, 1922’ in *LCW* 36, 571–575 on 574 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1922/mar/26.htm>>, para. 14 and 16: “The essential is not in institutions, not in reorganisations, not in new decrees, but in the *selection of personnel* and in *checking performance*.”

⁷⁶ “[D]epartments are shit, decrees are shit. Find people, check up on work – these are everything.” (February 21, 1922) in *PSS* 44, 369 & <<http://leninvi.com/t44/p369/>>. [„Ведомства – говно; декреты – говно. Искать людей, проверять работу – в этом все.”]

⁷⁷ We may think of the construction of the technique of appeal in the Turkish Empire—Martin Shapiro ‘Islam and Appeal’ [1980] <<https://scholarship.law.berkeley.edu/facpubs/1353/>>, reprinted in *Comparative Legal Cultures* ed. Varga, 299–330—or the role of a ‘revisor’ or ‘central envoy’ in provincial Russia. Early and later phases of administrative development in the Russian countryside are described by John P. LeDonne ‘Russian Governors General, 1775-1825: Territorial or Functional Administration?’ *Cahiers du monde russe* 42 (2001) 1, 5–30 resp. John N. Hazard ‘Unity and Diversity in Socialist Law’ *Law and Contemporary Problems* 30 (1965) 2, 270–290 & <<https://scholarship.law.duke.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3056&context=lcp>>.

⁷⁸ Lenin ‘»Dual« Subordination and Legality’ (May 20, 1922) in *LCW* 33 & <<http://www.marx2mao.com/PDFs/Lenin CW-Vol. 33.pdf>>, 363–367 at 364, 365, 365 & 366: “law cannot be Kaluga law or Kazan law {standing, symbolically, for administrative units with millions of inhabitants – Cs.V.}, but [...] it must be uniform all-Russia law, and even uniform for the entire federation of Soviet Republic” / “The procurator must see to it that not a single decision passed by any local authority runs counter to the law, and only from this aspect is it his duty to challenge every illegal decision.” / “Unless we strictly adhere to this most elementary condition for maintaining the uniformity of the law for the whole Federation, it will be utterly impossible to protect the law, or to develop any kind of culture.” / „establish real uniformity in the application of the laws throughout the Republic, and throughout the Federation.”

⁷⁹ Burbank, 37–44.

⁸⁰ Then, the Socialist Revolutionary Party was in majority. Of course, Lenin reacted this way: “We’ll tell the people that its interests are higher than the interests of democratic institutions. There’s no need to go back to the old prejudices, which subordinated the interests of the people to formal democratism” in *PSS* 35, 137, quoted by Burbank, 38, note 66.

November 1918 on, also for “more exact observance of the law”.⁸¹ Accordingly, other interpretations simply disprize this move as state-centered nihilism with no genuine germs of legalism.⁸²

4. The Nature of Bolshevik Law

For Lenin, “Laws are political measures, politics.”⁸³ A reduction like this amounts to denaturation, disowning the law’s autonomy.⁸⁴ This is a case when ‘law’ ceases to be law indeed. On the other hand, what would a law entirely politicized be like? Well, simply: dictatorship—that is, unrestricted power, founded on sheer violence, in want of whatever rules. This is what Lenin professes—practices and makes practiced—from the turn of the century.⁸⁵ Externally, it looks like revolutionary expediency, and internally, arbitrariness. Providing you have other ground, on what can you rely at all? Lenin’s answer is clear-cut and opaque at the same time: “our morality is entirely subordinated to the interests of the proletariat’s class struggle. Our morality stems from the interests of the class struggle of the proletariat.”⁸⁶ Then, morality as the substitute value for law is nothing but pure interest.

Brain and action center of the revolution? All things considered, state machinery and Bolshevik party proved functionally one and the same.⁸⁷

⁸¹ E.g., Lenin ‘Immediate Tasks of Soviet Government’ (April 1918) in *PSS* 36, 165–208; and further on, *PSS* 37, 21; *PSS* 36, 315; *PSS* 37, 129.

⁸² Eugene Huskey ‘A Framework for the Analysis of Soviet Law’ *The Russian Review* 50 (January 1991) 1, 53–70.

⁸³ Lenin ‘A Caricature of Marxism and Imperialist Economism’ (early Autumn, 1916) in *LCW* 23, 28–76 <<http://www.marx2mao.com/Lenin/CM16.html>> on 48.

Dedicated to the centenary of Lenin’s birth, the Soviet Academy of Sciences Institute of State and Law commissioned the Hungarian partner institute to contribute a part—»Ленин о революционное правотворчество«—to the collective volume *В. И. Ленин о социалистическом государстве и праве* ред. В. М. Чхиквадзе & Б. Н. Топорнин (Москва: Наука 1969). The papers by Szabó Imre ‘Lenin a jogról és a szocialista jogról’ [Lenin on law and socialist law] and Kulcsár Kálmán ‘A politika és a jog viszonya Lenin műveiben’ [Politics and law in Lenin’s oeuvre] emphasised Lenin identifying the law’s core in politics—*Állam-és Jogtudomány* XIII (1970) 1, 3–16 and 17–24. Imre Szabó writes in a similar text—‘Lénine et le droit’ *Revue internationale de Droit comparé* XXII (1970) 4, 685–686 on 685—: „dans l’esprit de Lénine le droit s’est présenté catégoriquement comme un moyen de la politique.”

⁸⁴ Cf. note 10.

⁸⁵ Lenin ‘The Victory of the Cadets and the Tasks of the Workers’ Party’ (1906) in *LCW* 10, 199–276 & <<http://www.marx2mao.com/Lenin/VCTWP06.html>> on 247: “[A]uthority untrammelled by any laws, absolutely unrestricted by any rules whatever, and based directly on force. The term ‘dictatorship’ has no other meaning but this”. Lenin *The Proletarian Revolution and the Renegade Kautsky* (October–November 1918) (Peking: Foreign Language Press 1972) 144 on 12: “Dictatorship is rule based directly upon force and unrestricted by any laws. The revolutionary dictatorship of the proletariat is rule won and maintained by the use of violence by the public against the bourgeoisie, rule that is unrestricted by any laws”. Lenin ‘On the Tasks of the People’s Commissariat for Justice Under the New Economic Policy: Letter to D. I. Kursky’ (February 20, 1922) in *LCW* 36, 560–565 at 562–563 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1922/feb/20c.htm>>: “[I]t is we—we conscious workers, we Communists—who are the state.”

⁸⁶ Lenin ‘The Tasks of the Youth Leagues’ (October 2, 1920) in Lenin *LCW* 31 <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1920/oct/02.htm>>.

⁸⁷ “Such an organisation must perforce not be very extensive and must be as secret as possible.” Lenin ‘What is to be Done’ (1902) in Lenin *LCW* 5 in <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1901/witbd/iv.htm>>. Cf.

Anything ‘law’ was indeed party law—a Bolshevik party product, originating from a private organisation, in conception, style, and thought-patterns as well.

“Essentially, they imposed on the entire population the rules and procedures they had adopted for their Bolshevik organization when it had been a private and voluntary body, making the private public and the voluntary coercive. Although they never succeeded in providing it with a theoretical foundation, the one-party state proved to be the most enduring and influential of their accomplishments.”⁸⁸

Lenin’s law remained inseparable from violence and terrorism imposed. “It seems never to have occurred to Lenin that the root of [...] troubles lay in the fact that the whole system was based, as he constantly emphasized, on force and not on law.”⁸⁹ The bare fact indeed that this law worked in a terroristic framework may have blocked any genuinely legal effect. For such a background itself, composed of force, violence, and terror—as its very etymology, too, suggests⁹⁰—is just to arouse and awake the unceasing sense of danger. A sense of danger that can only encourage addressees to activate defensive mechanisms. And with effects in accumulation, public and private action, including the official acts of the state, all they fall a victim of this need for defensiveness, because of the law’s symbiotic, at the same time protective and threatening prospects.

No need to say that the association of political action with the practice of brutality and terrorism was a central constituent of Lenin’s political credo from his youth on.⁹¹ It was in 1905 that he opted for mass terror, and not because individual terror made his brother executed, but because he belittled it as not effective enough. Nor did he hesitate resorting to terrorism for causing panic or fear, or simply for silencing.⁹² In July 1918, he commanded the Petrograd leader

also Maria Łos *Communist Ideology, Law and Crime* A Comparative View of the USSR and Poland New York: St. Martin’s Press 1988) xv + 353 at 4–7.

⁸⁸ Pipes, 151.

⁸⁹ Kolakowski, 489.

⁹⁰ E.g., *terreo* means ‘frighten; harass; perturb’ according to F. E. J. Valpy *An Etymological Dictionary of the Latin Language* (London: Baldwin / Longman / Whittaker 1828) viii + 550 on 471; and *terrēre* stands for ‘to cause fear to occur’ or, earlier on, ‘to cause to shiver’, from the roots of **tres/*trem*, according to Alain Christol ‘Lexical Consequences of a Phonetic Law’ in *New Studies in Latin Linguistics* Selected Papers from the 4th International Colloquium on Latin Linguistics, Cambridge, April 1987, ed. Robert Coleman (Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publ. Co. 1991) x + 477 [Studies in Language Companion Series 21] on 55.

⁹¹ When in 1891, the Volga famine (with nearly half a million deaths; cf. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russian_famine_of_1891%E2%80%939392>) led her sister to give a helping hand, he turned cynically, and even shocked his entourage by rejoicing that at least the czarism would be unveiled again. Алексей Александрович Беляков *Юность вождя* [The adolescence of the leader] Воспоминания современника В. И. Ленина ([Москва]: Мол. гвардия 1958) 110 at 80–82 [A. Belyakov *Yunost vozhdy* (Moscow: Molodaya gvardiya)].

⁹² Raphael Cohen-Almagor ‘Foundations of Violence, Terror and War in the Writings of Marx, Engels, and Lenin’ *Terrorism and Political Violence* 3 (1991) 2, 1–24, quote from <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1339145>, 25: “Lenin affirmed not only the use of violence but also the resort to terroristic activities [...] he allowed the use of acts which intended to arouse panic

GRIGORY ZINOVIEV to resort to mass terror,⁹³ which he sometimes used as a suppletory to legitimate authority as well.

Lenin's basic mentality was both a-humane and anti-humane, simply cruel. When he contemplated actioning, his first alternative was always a terroristic measure.⁹⁴ Even his regulatory measures were complemented by providing framework for terror or discretionary adjudication. When drafting the Criminal Code, he instructed his Commissar of Justice that

“The courts must not ban terror—to promise that would be deception or self-deception—but must formulate the motives underlying it, legalise it as a principle, plainly, without any make-believe or embellishment. It must be formulated in the broadest possible manner, for only revolutionary law and revolutionary conscience can more or less widely determine the limits within which it should be applied.”⁹⁵

Perhaps what is the most extremist, pathologic, and anti-human in all the above is the fact that terroristic threatening is so strong and explicit that law and terror turn to be inseparable—almost interchangeable—from one another, with any of them ready anytime to switch over to the other. After all,

“Terror became with him an administrative technique, a simple way of solving problems and achieving results when conventional means failed; armed with terror, the Vecheka served as the Party's all-purpose agency, as the short cut to a given end.”⁹⁶

In order to strengthen the dialectic unity of terror and law as described above, Lenin declared at the end of 1917 that nothing could be exempt from subordination to the revolutionary cause, not even what the Soviet power itself ordered, be it human integrity or election result or parliamentary decision.⁹⁷

In the end, as a closing sarcasm of the drama, it turned out that Bolsheviki, having achieved totally uncheckable power of decree-issuing, practically arrived back exactly whereto, by launching their revolution, they had departed two weeks ago, to what had been hated as the “Muscovite patrimonial absolutism's” *ukaz*-government. What is more, even decree-government became privatized in that, from then on, instead of the monarch as the state's representation, the

and fear amongst specific target groups.” One of the Soviet justice leaders (also executed in 1938), NIKOLAI KRYLENKO opined, in testimony of the bloody experience they introduced: “We must execute not only the guilty. Execution of the innocent will impress the masses even more.”

⁹³ PSS 50, 106.

⁹⁴ Joan Witte ‘Violence in Lenin's Thought and Practice: The Spark and the Conflagration’ *Terrorism and Political Violence* 5 (1993) 3, 135–203: “Lenin evinced an addiction to violence that caused him to overlook or foreclose other, less radical, political methods for accomplishing his goals.”

⁹⁵ Lenin ‘To D. I. Kursky’ (May 17, 1922) *LCW* 33, 358–359 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1922/may/17.htm>> on 358.

⁹⁶ Leggett *The Cheka*, 169–170.

⁹⁷ Lenin (note 42).

Bolshevik party as “a private body [...], a self-contained and self-perpetuating body, accountable only to itself” was to rule.⁹⁸

In this way, Lenin built an arrangement which was elitist, conspiratively operated, regardlessly dedicated to a single-minded one-cause, in a manner thoroughly MACHIAVELLIAN and terror-based. And its law perverted into a concurrent complementation of what was known as the express denial of law.⁹⁹

5. “Legalised lawlessness”

Let’s overthrow the hated power above all! The revolution generated chaos, and common sense was silenced. Extreme situations emerged that could be mitigated by new interventions only. Here is a prosaic description of everyday life, worth of remembering:

„When the Provisional Government assumed power after NICHOLAS II’s abdication, it set about instituting liberal reforms, including eliminating the tsar’s regular police. But dissolving this much-hated yet efficient police force and replacing it with a new municipal police led rapidly to the breakdown of order and services. Amid the chaos, crime flourished. Gangs of criminals, deserters, and hooligans brazenly roamed the streets. Mass prison escapes became common. And vigilantism spread widely as ordinary citizens felt compelled to take the law into their own hands, often meting out mob justice on suspected wrongdoers. [...] The Bolsheviks swept into power in the October Revolution but had no practical plans to reestablish order. As crime continued to escalate and violent alcohol riots almost drowned the revolutionary regime, they redefined it as »counterrevolutionary activity«, to be dealt with by the secret police, whose harshly repressive, extralegal means of enforcement helped pave the way for a Communist dictatorship.”¹⁰⁰

⁹⁸ Pipes, 152 resp. 15: “The system of legislation the Bolsheviks set in place within two weeks of the October coup, for all its revolutionary rhetoric, marked a reversion to the autocratic practices of tsarist Russia before the Manifesto of October 17, 1905.” Cf. also <<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ukase>> and NICHOLAS II *Манифест об усовершенствовании государственного порядка* <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/October_Manifesto>, which served as a foreplay for a constitution.

⁹⁹ Lenin “continued to lean in favour of dictatorship, terror, a one-party and one-ideology state, massive state economic ownership, a class-biased social system and legal nihilism.” He even conspired in his party when he organised his terrorist organisation and then freed it from any responsibility (cf. note 96). Even in his state actions—insensitively to either forms or ordered frameworks—he valued nothing but revolutionary activism and, in case of measures taken, efficiency. Lenin issued decrees by himself, unassisted, knowing no democratic filters but conspiratoriality: many a time he drafted, signed and made them signed, and as the immense territory’s new laws they were published within hours. Notably, “they passed important decrees to each other for co-signature. Lenin wrote as chairman of Sovnarkom, SVERDLOV as secretary of the Party Central Committee or frequently as chairman of the Presidium of the Central Executive Committee of the Congress of Soviets.” Robert Service *Lenin A Political Life*, 3 (Houndmills & London: Macmillan 1995) xxi + 393, xv, 59, resp. 243–245.

¹⁰⁰ Pl. Tsuyoshi Hasegawa *Crime and Punishment in the Russian Revolution Mob Justice and Police in Petrograd* (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Belknap Press of the Harvard University Press 2017) 368.

After all, as instigated by Lenin,¹⁰¹ a “civil war [was] fought with legalized lawlessness” against the people themselves.¹⁰² From the moment of seizing power, revolutionary courts were established that began annihilating “the enemy”.¹⁰³ Realizing that their revenging and terrifying production of death toll could not be massive enough, an extraordinary terror machine—the Cheka—was established on December 5, 1917, extended as an immense institutional network throughout the country by September 1918. Future victims were searched for according to labels like ‘enemies of the people’, ‘hidden enemies’, or ‘suspect social origin’.¹⁰⁴ The new Soviet science of justice may have proudly proclaimed by Lenin’s critical age that the workers’ and peasants’ Leninist paradise already institutionalized revolutionary tribunals endowed with “a complete liberty of repression [...] not bound by anything in selection of punishment [...] no procedure but shooting”, in pair with the Cheka (which they established with no legal authorization, moreover, with no mention at all in any juridical document until November 1918), proceeding to reach “final decision [...] with no appeal against it [...] and [...] with no rule settling either the jurisdiction or the procedure”.¹⁰⁵ Or, as stipulated on January 1, 1918, “The Revolutionary Tribunal shall take into consideration the circumstances of the case and the dictates of revolutionary conscience when deciding punishment.”¹⁰⁶

What such a judiciary may have been like? According to staff data available concerning the years of 1934–1935, 51,1% of the judges were in want of

¹⁰¹ “Dictatorship is a state of intensified war. [...] Until the final issue is decided, this awful state of war will continue. And we say: »*À la guerre comme à la guerre*; we do not promise any freedom, or any democracy.«” — Lenin ascertained at the Third Congress of the Communist International [*Pravda* (July 5, 1921) 144 & <<https://www.marxists.org/archive/lenin/works/1921/jun/12.htm>>. [„Диктатура есть состояние обостренной войны. [...] Пока нет общего окончательного результата, будет продолжаться состояние ужасной войны. И мы говорим: «На войне мы поступаем по-военному: мы не обещаем никакой свободы и никакой демократии.»” in *PSS* & <<http://uaio.ru/vil/44.htm>>, 53–54.]

¹⁰² Richard Pipes *Legalized Lawlessness Soviet Revolutionary Justice* (London: Institute for European Defence & Strategic Studies 1986) 24.

¹⁰³ Lenin’s People’s Commissar for Justice (until March 1918)—cf. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Isaac_Steinberg>—still asks him: why does he not call his office the People’s Commissariat for Social Extermination? And Lenin is neither shocked, nor surprised; he knows best what is his purpose... Isaac Steinberg *In the Workshop of the Revolution* (New York: Rinehart 1953) 306 on 155, quoted by *The Black Book of Communism Crimes, Terror, Repression*, ed. Stéphane Courtois et al. (Cambridge, Mass. & London: Harvard University Press 1999) xx + 858 on 61.

¹⁰⁴ Matthew Rendle ‘Revolutionary Tribunals and the Origins of Terror in Early Soviet Russia’ *Historical Research* 84 (November 2011), No. 226, 693–271. Labeling was routinised by Lenin. Just a few months earlier he had published an article on »The enemies of the people«—*Pravda* (June 7, 1917), 75—in praise of the Jacobin terror, which “must be applied to the revolutionary class of the twentieth century” (*LCW* 25, 57–58), too.

Soon rank and file self-accusing Communists would add to the enemies to be destroyed. As to the “whether it is right or wrong, it is my party” mentality of them, see Arthur Koestler *Darkness at Noon* (London: Jonathan Cape 1940) 254 and also Richard Landes *Heaven on Earths The Varieties of the Millennial Experience* (Oxford: Oxford University Press 2011), 335, ch. 11 on »Totalitarian millennialism: the Bolshevik apocalypse«.

¹⁰⁵ Николай Васильевич Крыленко *Судоустройство РСФСР* [Court system of the R.S.F.S.R.] (Лекции по теории и истории судоустройства) (Москва: [Юрид. изд-во НКЮ] 1923) 406 at 100, 205 & 322–323 [N. V. Krylenko *Sudoustroistvo RSFSR* (lektsii po teorii i istorii sudoustroistva) (Moskva: [Iuridicheskoe izdatel'stva NKIU])].

¹⁰⁶ *The Russian Revolution and the Soviet State 1917–1921* (Documents) ed. Martin McCauley (London: Macmillan 1975) xiv + 315 [Studies in Russian and East European History] on 182, para. 2.

whatever previous training, 41,7% had some six months' and 1,8% one-year's course relating to law; and only 5,8% were law school graduates. According to another statistics, 84,6% of lower court and 62,2% of higher court justices grew up having barely attended elementary school.¹⁰⁷

The end result is thought-provoking. Today's estimates suggest that there could be 200,000 victims of the red terror, in addition to 2,000,000 of those executed between 1917 and 1923. In striking comparison with the era just transcended, the total number of victims for the entire last half-century of the tsarist rule was 14.000.¹⁰⁸

6. Personal Features

It is hard not to be interested in the key personalities involved in basic turns of history. In our case, a number of reminiscences, memoirs and scholarly treatments concerning especially the triad—mentioned earlier—of MARX, Lenin and LUKÁCS offers remarkable notes and considerations, mainly as to their one-cause devotion, unremitting pursuit of the goal, complemented by the distorting reductionist fixity deforming the whole personality concerned.¹⁰⁹

Although noted about MARX, Lenin too is characterized by being blindly alienated not only from real environments, but that even his main occupation was “totally and incorrigibly deskbound.”¹¹⁰ And what he produced under the aegis of writing on ‘scientific socialism’ is simply unassessable in a scholarly perspective. For in his case, too, “The whole approach is one of vindication, not investigation, but it is a vindication of something proclaimed as the perfect truth with the conviction not of the scientist but of the believer.”¹¹¹ All in all, in contrast to scholarly approaches, his “advocatory and not explanatory” protagonism is barely more than wishful thinking.¹¹²

¹⁰⁷ *Советское государство* [Sovetskoe gosudarstvo] 1936/5, 115 resp. *Советская юстиция* [Sovietskaia Iustitsiia] 15 (1935) 35, 4–5; quoted by Lapenna *State and Law*, 41 note 156.

With the exception of the highest governing body, consisting of one and a half dozen key figures, all university graduates, half of them lawyers or economists. Rigby *Lenin's Government*, 93.

¹⁰⁸ Gregory Claeys *Dystopia: A Natural History A Study of Modern Despotism, its Antecedents, and its Literary Diffractions* (Oxford: Oxford University Press 2017) x + 556 on 134. Half a century earlier, an official summation for the last half-century of czarism counted 14,000 executions, and involving prison and pogrom incidents, all in all 40,000 victims. During Lenin's six years in Soviet leadership, there were 200,000 executions, and involving prison and uprising retaliation events, a total of 500,000 deaths. Robert Conquest ‘The Human Cost of Soviet Communism’ in *Document* No. 92-36 (92nd Congress, 1st Session) of the United States Senate, Committee on the Judiciary, Sub-Committee to Investigate the Administration of the Internal Security Act and other Internal Security Laws (16 July 1971), 5–33 at 22–23.

¹⁰⁹ See Michael Löwy *Rédemption et utopie Le judaïsme libertaire en Europe centrale; Une étude d'affinité élective* (Paris: Presses Universitaires de France 1988) 258 [Sociologie d'aujourd'hui].

¹¹⁰ Paul Johnson *Intellectuals* (New York: Harper & Row 1988) x + 385 on 60.

¹¹¹ Karl Jaspers ‘Marx und Freud’ *Der Monat* 3 (1950), No. 36, 141–150.

¹¹² Tama Weisman *Hannah Arendt and Karl Marx On Totalitarianism and the Tradition of Western Political Thought* (Lanham, Maryland: Lexington Books 2014) xiv + 173 in ch 1, 1–10.

A common feature of Lenin's exceedingly negative personality pictures is the total lack of a sophisticated virtue, known as *sophrosyne* in antiquity. This is "an ideal of excellence of character and soundness of mind", associated with virtues like temperance, moderation, prudence, purity, decorum, and self-control. In context of the PYTHAGOREAN *harmonia*, PLATO claimed it equals moral sanity.¹¹³ It is maybe obvious that such deprivation may have some consequences; especially in case when those hiatus is refilled with hate.¹¹⁴

A case study has found that Lenin was a personality type characterizable as "aggressive, authoritarian, and completely detached from the values of the Western civilization", in sum, a „pathological [whose] abnormality is only apparent from a democratic point of view."¹¹⁵ Others have drawn conclusions from his oeuvre. Accordingly, he may have been „infatuated with revolution as a purpose of struggle and conflict", in which there was „the idea over-valued" that got fixed. Finally, his achievement may have been circular inasmuch as he "disorganized and destroyed in order to *seize power* and, in turn, used power to disorganize and destroy."¹¹⁶

More historical overviews note, for instance, that

“he promised people anything and everything. He offered simple solutions to complex problems. He lied unashamedly. He identified a scapegoat he could later label »enemies of the people«. He justified himself on the basis that winning meant everything.”¹¹⁷

Such portrayals draw attention to traits like arguing with enemy images that he instantly produced through demonization, renewed and adapted from moment to moment; or to his ratiocination stemmed from the amoralism of "Ends justify the means"; or, again, to his starring tactics of "The firstest with the mostest". Lenin brake promises when, for instance, he had pledged peasants free land ownership but immediately issued more than half-a-hundred decrees to end private property, accompanied by a secret directive, too, to destroy state archives of land, factory, and building title deeds. And not the least he played with words

¹¹³ <<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sophrosyne>>. In contrasted qualities of *aphrosunē/sōphrosunē*, see Nancy Sherman *The Fabric of Character Aristotle's Theory of Virtue* (Oxford: Clarendon 1989) xiv + 213 on 107. According to Scott Carson—<<https://www.encyclopedia.com/humanities/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/sophrosune>>—this noun "is related to the verb *sōphronein*, combining *sōs*, safe, and *phronein*, to think". CICERO translated it by four qualities into Latin: *temperantia*, *moderatio*, *modestia*, and *frugalitas*.

¹¹⁴ George H. Leggett 'Lenin, Terror and Political Police' *Survey* 21 (Autumn 1975) 4, 157–184 on 174 summarises in a way that "The key to understanding the Red Terror and the Cheka system lies essentially in Lenin's doctrine and Lenin's character." As known, the driving force behind Lenin's aspirations was the hate of anything prevalent.

¹¹⁵ Zevedei Barbu *Democracy and Dictatorship Their Psychology and Patterns* [1956] (Abingdon: Routledge 2000) 284 [The International Library of Sociology: Political Sociology] on 262 resp. 263.

¹¹⁶ Stefan Thomas Possony *Lenin The Compulsive Revolutionary* (Chicago: Regnery [1964]) 418 [The Hoover Institution Series].

¹¹⁷ Victor Sebestyen *Lenin the Dictator An Intimate Portrait* (London: Weidenfeld & Nicolson 2017) xix + 569, overviewed by Roland Elliott Brown 'How Lenin Manipulated the Russian Revolution to his Own Ends' [review] *The Spectator* (March 2017) <<https://www.spectator.co.uk/2017/03/how-lenin-manipulated-the-russian-revolution-to-his-own-ends/>>.

to mislead people; usually he went to disarm opponents by manipulating meanings. “By controlling words, Lenin controlled perceptions of reality.”¹¹⁸

7. The End of the Game

Drawing a balance is exciting but rather sensitive an issue. The whole bulk of Lenin’s writings was revolving around how to transform society, still the suspicion can hardly be denied that MARXISM, forerunners and late followers altogether, has been most like a caricature of itself, since its very conception. Although identifying itself as the natural science of society,¹¹⁹ it was overwhelmed by the hatred of anything prevailing, counterbalanced by Utopian dreaming. Lenin dedicated all his energies to seize power. A fetish target of endmost targets, he fixated it as a heavenly gate: by passing through, you will have consummated what humankind could. In such a theorizing based on extrapolative generalizations¹²⁰ guided by dogmas¹²¹ to end in dreams, breakthrough of the gate became the substitute to arrival, worth glory itself. As if construction upon the ruins of destruction could come almost automatically; as if grabbing power could be anything more than sheer opportunity to start governing.

Due to Lenin, in an incredibly short period the new power returned to the hatefully rejected *ukaz*-government of czarism, moreover, in this new decree-governmental absolutism he made the Bolshevik party play a dual role: albeit not a democratically representative public law body, this apparently civil corps could ultimately define what the new legislation, government and judiciary were to do. In 1921, the rebellion at Kronstadt came precisely to denying this. War communism and civil wars arose the navy for reconsidering the Russian dream, next to capital Petrograd. Its blood sacrifice stood for “a utopian participatory democracy [...], capable of self-determination and imbued with the ideals of creating a new society without parties or ruler”,¹²² in which they were ready to die “for the power of Soviets, not parties.”¹²³ Their fifteen-point program

¹¹⁸ Monica Showalter ‘Six Principles of Propaganda Lenin Used to Consolidate Power’ *Investor’s Business Daily* Commentary (September 20, 2013) <<https://www.investors.com/politics/commentary/lenin-used-six-principles-of-propaganda-to-consolidate-control/>>.

¹¹⁹ For apologetics, cf. Kenneth Neill Cameron *Marxism: The Science of Society* An Introduction [1985] (New York: International Publishers 1993) xvi + 245 and Michael Burawoy ‘Marxism as Science: Historical Challenges and Theoretical Growth’ *American Sociological Review* 55 (December 1990), 775–793.

¹²⁰ E.g., H. B. Mayo ‘Marxist Theory and Scientific Methods’ *The Canadian Journal of Economics and Political Science / Revue canadienne d’Économique et de Science politique* 18 (November 1952) 4, 487–499.

¹²¹ E.g., Gavin Kitching *Marxism and Science* Analysis of an Obsession (University Park, Pa.: Penn State University Press 2005) xii + 258.

¹²² Eric Sonnicksen ‘Utopia in Revolution: The Kronstadt Republic and the End of the Soviet Dream’ (July 1, 2013) in <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2288045>>.

¹²³ Radio of March 6; Alexander Berkman *The Kronstadt Rebellion* ([Berlin]: [Der Syndikalist] [1922]) [Russian Revolution series 3] in <<https://www.marxists.org/reference/archive/berkman/1922/kronstadt-rebellion/ch4.htm>>, ch. 4.

projected a genuinely *Soviet* election and power, that is, the elimination of one-party rule and dictatorship, embodied by the Leninist version of the Soviets.¹²⁴

When STALIN came in power, debating on law greatly reduced.¹²⁵ In 1938, with concurrent theoreticians liquidated, VYSHINSKIY launched the STALINist understanding of Soviet law.¹²⁶ It transformed into an immense and stiffened institutional network of what Lenin had practiced as law. This may explain how “the regulatory and institutionbuilding strategy that [Lenin] advanced was a failure, and that in turn it exacerbated bureaucratization and engineered the peculiar union of authoritarianism and bureaucracy that became the hallmark of Soviet society.”¹²⁷

So Lenin made law a servile companion of politics. Emptied from self-securing marks whilst made flexible enough to cover or exact power manipulations, it was transmuted into a proceduralized complementation of non-law, that is, of illicit, lawless measures. Thereby „Lenin’s idea of law as a manipulable instrument of politics deprived it of the »majesty« and the aura of »justice« that could have made law, over time, an effective arm of the socialist state in Russia.”¹²⁸

Russian/Soviet law has mostly remained a dictate of autocracy for popular understanding. In contrast to the West’s reception of law—acknowledged as the ultimate effective factor of social integration, allowing for coexistence by providing *do ut des*¹²⁹ framework for individuals to live in society—, it is rather perceived as a constraint on all, injected from outside and from above. So ordinary people had better to avoid contacting it, because it had an alien potential, threatening anyone ascribed to it.¹³⁰

¹²⁴ A most successful military commander of the time in Soviet Russia, the twenty-eight-year-old TUKHACHEVSKIY headed a punitive campaign one week after the release of this program, with an outnumbered army but with twelve-thousands-man loss of life on his own side. A few thousands of volunteer party workers were hired into this campaign force, due to widespread distrust in those uniformed. “There can be no Soviet power without the Communist party”—vowed those volunteers in their foolish hustle hours later, losing four-fifth of their strength in fight against those who were to die for the cause of “All Power to Soviets and Not to Parties”. Israel Getzler *Kronstadt 1917–1921 The Fate of a Soviet Democracy* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 1983) xii + 296 [Soviet and East European Studies] on 244.

¹²⁵ E.g., Michael Head ‘The Passionate Legal Debates of the Early Years of the Russian Revolution’ *Canadian Journal of Law and Jurisprudence* 14 (January 2001) 1, 3–27, Abstract: “After 1924, the consolidation of the STALINist regime increasingly meant an end to the open discussion of law and legal theory. From genuine debate, by the 1930s the dialogue became reduced to diatribes and denunciations.”

¹²⁶ See, e.g., Robert Sharlet & Piers Beirne ‘In Search of Vyshinsky: The Paradox of Law and Terror’ in *Revolution in Law* ed. Beirne, 136–156. For the theoretical consequences, see Csaba Varga ‘Quelques problèmes de la définition du droit dans la théorie socialiste du droit’ *Archives de Philosophie du Droit* XII (Paris: Sirey 1967), 189–205 {reprint in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/15500/15541>>, 10–26}.

¹²⁷ Beirne & Hunt, 602.

¹²⁸ Burbank, 43–44. Such a failed result was predefined by the first moments of the coup: “the dismissal of parliamentary government and the encouragement given to violent land seizures served to undermine the very fragile sense of a rule of law in Russia.” White, 136.

¹²⁹ Cf. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quid_pro_quo>.

¹³⁰ Even recently, Hungarian ethnographers from Covasna (Transylvania) visiting remote village settlements in Moldavia (Soviet-dominated for half a century) have found locals running away from foreign sight: almost trembling from encountering anyone alien, as if he/she were a malignant human, representative of the self-interested coercive state.

This is so much so that even international development agencies, either donoring or mentoring, are beware of advising them anything to be drafted in form of legal regulation.¹³¹ Recent empirical research confirms this. Even now, three decades after the red dictatorship fell, Russian scholars cannot anticipate more than phase to phase development toward a new kind of dual state, that is, a new variant of what ERNST FRAENKEL had described as the property of the Nazi regime: dictatorship in power manifestations and classical rule of law wherever the quest is politically irrelevant.¹³² Perhaps the fact is also messaging that post-Soviet legal scholarship is mostly silent about the issue. Instead, it is rather concerned with exploring Christian roots within a new Russian discipline, called »culturology«.¹³³

8. Conclusion

Lenin's oeuvre was, from the law's viewpoint, its extreme and inexorable instrumentation for power engineering, first in the Russian political theory of Marxism, based on the antecedent of anarchism, and then as a tragic end in the Bolshevik revolutionary practice of one of the world's largest countries. Forced by state violence, various normative settlements can be effected, but not all of them is able to serve social integration. In terms of the adequacy of purpose and means, Lenin's legal ideal and practice proved to be the next derailment following an ossified tsarism, and at the same time an alarming historical example of the neglect of the law's own needs.

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¹³¹ Kathryn Hendley 'Legal Development in Post-Soviet Russia' *Post-Soviet Affairs*, 13 (1997) 3, 228–251, quoted by Csaba Varga 'Reception of Legal Patterns in a Globalising Age' in *Globalization, Law and Economy Proceedings of the 22nd IVR World Congress, IV*, ed. Nicolás López Calera (Stuttgart: Franz Steiner Verlag 2007), 85–96 [ARSP Beiheft 109] {reprint in <<http://mek.oszk.hu/17500/17543>>, 21–41}.

¹³² Kathryn Hendley '»Telephone Law« and »the Rule of Law«: The Russian Case' *Hague Journal on the Rule of Law* 1 (2009), 241–262 at 246–249 resp. 260–261; cf. also Ernst Fraenkel *The Dual State A Contribution to the Theory of Dictatorship* (New York: Oxford University Press 1941) xvi + 248.

¹³³ Cf. <<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Culturology>> as well as Csaba Varga 'Comparatist Movement Reborn, Or the Relativity of Where the Centre and the Periphery Are' in *Філософія порівняльного правознавства Збірник наукових праць*, ред. О. В. Кресін (Київ & Львів: Ліга-прес 2015), 506–526 {in Hungarian in <http://jura.ajk.pte.hu/JURA_2014_1.pdf>, 189–193}.

Marlène Laruelle 'The Discipline of Culturology: A New »Ready-Made Thought« for Russia' *Diogenes* 51 (November 2004) 4, 21–36 & <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/249742640_The_Discipline_of_Culturology_A_New_%27Ready-Made-Thought%27_for_Russia> on 26 resp. 35 note 13 mentions the function of "erasure" by remarking that effects of tsarism-cum-STALINISM on law are "missing from all analyses because they are thought irrelevant to expression of the 'essence' of national identity".

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